

Self-identity for a Successful Career

Hello, I am Hiếu ...

UCLA, Stanford, UPenn, & Harvard

Forbes VN 30 Under 30 –2016

Leaders at G.A.P Institute & MAX Edu

Strategic Consultant at Deloitte & BCG

Former Director of Marketing & Admissions at VinUniversity

My dream: “to help 1 million Vietnamese students **go global**”

My 18's at UCLA

“The only things you can control in your life are your attitude & efforts.”

4 QUESTIONS of your life

- 1. What is worth knowing?*
- 2. What is worth doing?*
- 3. What makes for a good human life?*
- 4. What are my responsibilities to other people?*

Professor Barry Schwartz
Author of Best-Seller “The Paradox of Choice”

3 things to focus your

MINDSET on:

1. *Self-awareness*

2. *Self-discipline*

3. *Self-happiness*

 Forbes

"VẤN ĐỀ LỚN NHẤT ĐỐI VỚI
NGƯỜI TRẺ VIỆT NAM LÀ
GIÁO DỤC. GIÁO DỤC TẠO RA
CƠ HỘI BÌNH ĐẲNG
CHO MỌI NGƯỜI."

30 UNDER 30

Lê Đình Hiếu, 28

Trưởng nhóm Global Shapers TP. HCM
(Curator of Global Shapers HCMC)

3 SKILLS to level up yourself

1. Ask the right questions

2. Be in the right network

3. Find the right motivation

Personal Brand Week
Your name is just the start.

eBook

PRICEWATERHOUSECOOPERS

Link download:

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/maxscholarshipforall/posts/3048884212032789/>

Group “Scholarship for all”:

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/sanhocbongcungmax>

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THANK YOU